

OPTICAL SOURCES

Nurullayev Ye.Ye.

Urgench branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named
after Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi.

elamannurullayev@gmail.com

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Abstract: This thesis explores the pivotal role of semiconductor devices, including diode lasers and LEDs, in fiber optic communication. These devices, operating through direct modulation of current, serve as efficient and integral light sources. The study emphasizes the superiority of semiconductor lasers, particularly distributed feedback (DFB) lasers, for high-speed, long-distance communication due to their narrow spectral widths. Despite limitations, vertical cavity surface emitting lasers (VCSELs) show promise for integration, underscoring the ongoing evolution of optical communication technologies.

The role of the optical source is to generate light energy that once modulated carries the information across the fiber. Although there are a multitude of ways to generate light, in almost all fiber optic systems a semiconductor device is used for this purpose. These devices include diode lasers and light-emitting diodes (LEDs). There are many reasons for using these devices. For one thing, they are generally easy to operate and integrate with electronic circuits. From a circuit standpoint, diode lasers and LEDs all behave like a diode. In order to turn them on, a forward voltage must be applied to them, which in turn results in a current flow, which in turn will turn the device on. To increase the optical power, all we need to do is to increase the current. To turn the device off, we just need to turn off the diode by shutting down the current. Thus, in many applications the modulation of light is achieved by directly modulating the current flow through the device.

This method, called direct modulation, is very convenient and can be utilized up to modulation rates of several gigahertz. Figure 1. shows a simple circuit for converting an electric signal to an optical signal using a semiconductor laser.

Fig. 1. Simplified laser driver circuit

The circuit converts the voltage of the source to a proportional current signal that flows through the laser. Because the laser behaves more or less linearly above its threshold current, the voltage signal is converted to a similar optical signal. Although this simple circuit has several shortcomings, it serves well to illustrate the basic idea behind a laser driver.

Another advantage of semiconductor lasers is that these devices are generally very efficient light sources. Semiconductor lasers are characterized by their threshold current and slope efficacy. A typical semiconductor laser optimized for high-speed communication applications may have a threshold current of 5 mA and a slope efficiency of 0.5 mW/mA at room temperature. This means that it will start generating light as soon as the current flowing through it exceeds 5 mA. After that, the optical output power increases by 0.5 mW for every milliampere increase in current. Thus, at 10mA above threshold, this device can generate 5 mW of optical power. If we assume a forward voltage of 2 V, this represents a power dissipation of $2 \text{ V} \times 15 \text{ mA} = 30 \text{ mW}$. The overall efficiency of this device at this particular biasing point is $5/30 = 0.17$, which is not bad at all. Semiconductor devices also have an important advantage in terms of the optical wavelengths they produce. The wavelength generated or absorbed by a semiconductor is a function of its bandgap energy. The bandgap of semiconductors used in optoelectronics is in the range of 0.5–2 eV. This range corresponds to a wavelength range of approximately 500–4000 nm, which happens to include the wavelength windows of 1300 and 1500 nm, where the attenuation of glass fiber is minimum. Therefore, the light output of these devices can propagate in fibers for long distances with little attenuation.

Semiconductor devices are also very small in size, generally cheap, and very reliable. They can be produced in large quantities through wafer processing

techniques similar to other semiconductor devices. All these advantages make these devices ideal sources for numerous optical communication applications.

We mentioned that semiconductor light sources used in optical communications can be either LEDs or lasers. LEDs are cheaper, and thus they are mainly used in low data rates or short-reach applications. The main disadvantage of LEDs is that their light output has a wide spectrum width, which in turn causes high dispersion as the light propagates in the fiber. Dispersion causes the smearing of sharp edges in a signal as it propagates in the fiber and is directly proportional to the spectral width of the source. This is why LEDs cannot be used for long distance or high modulation rates in optical communication. Semiconductor lasers, on the other hand, have much narrower spectral widths, and therefore they are usually preferred in high-speed or long-reach links. In this book, we focus our discussions on lasers. The properties of these lasers depend on the materials used in constructing them as well as the physical and geometrical structures used in their design. Generally speaking, a laser is an optical oscillator, and an oscillator is realized by applying feedback to an amplifier. Semiconductor lasers can be divided into two main categories depending on the nature of this feedback.

In a Fabry–Perot (FP) laser, the feedback is provided by the two facets on the two sides of the active region. The optical cavity in FP lasers generally supports multiple wavelengths. Therefore, the output spectrum, although much narrower compared to an LED, still consists of several closely located peaks, or optical modes. A distributed feedback (DFB) laser, on other hand, includes additional structures that greatly attenuate all but one of those modes, and therefore a DFB laser comes closest to producing an ideal single wavelength output. This is why DFB lasers can minimize dispersion and support the longest attainable reaches.

Both FP and DFB lasers are edge-emitting devices, i.e., the light propagates in parallel to the semiconductor junction and comes out from the sides. A different structure is the vertical cavity surface emitting laser, or VCSEL. In a VCSEL the light output is perpendicular to the surface of the semiconductor. VCSELs are very attractive because of low threshold current and high efficiency. Moreover, many VCSELs can be integrated in the form of one-or two-dimensional arrays, a feature not available for edge-emitting devices.

However, VCSELs usually work at short wavelengths around 850 nm, a wavelength unfortunately unusable for long haul communication. Although research into production of VCSELs at longer wavelengths of 1300 and 1500 nm

is intense, such devices are still not available in an industrial scale. As a result, VCSELs like LEDs are usually used for short-distance links.

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